

GRID Security Review

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Abstract. A Computational GRID is a collection of heterogeneous computing resources spread across multiple administrative domains, serving the task of providing users with an easy access to these resources. Taking into account the advances in the area of high-speed networking, but also the increased computational power of current micro-processors, Computational GRIDs or meta-systems have gradually become more popular. However, together with the advantages that they exhibit they are also contributing to several problems associated with the design and implementation of a secure environment. The conventional approach to security, that of enforcing a single, system-wide policy, cannot be applied to large-scale distributed systems. This paper analyzes the security requirements of GRID Computing and reviews a number of security architectures that have been proposed. Furthermore, these architectures are evaluated in terms of addressing the major GRID security requirements that have been identified.

1 Introduction

Distributed Computing is all about harnessing unused computing resources, from across a computer network, so as to address workload challenges posed by demanding computer applications. During the last decade, Distributed Computing has matured from the notion of simple workload balancing to a ubiquitous solution that has been embraced by some of the world's leading organizations across multiple industry sectors.

While Distributed Computing harnessed the full potential of existing computer resources by effectively matching the supply of processing cycles with the demand created by applications, even more importantly it has paved the way for GRID Computing. As I. Foster, C. Kesselman and S. Tuecke state: "GRID Computing has emerged as an important new field, distinguished from conventional Distributed Computing by its focus on large-scale resource sharing, innovative application, and in some cases, high performance orientation" [1].

Although GRID Computing has, since mid 90's, gained the commercial, as well as the scientific, interest, its exact definition is not yet clear. According to I. Foster and

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C. Kesselman: “A Computational GRID is a hardware and software infrastructure that provides dependable, consistent, pervasive and inexpensive access to high-end computational capabilities” [2]. GRID Computing is concerned with coordinated resource sharing and problem solving in dynamic, multi-institutional virtual organizations. That sharing is not primarily file exchange but rather direct access to computers, software, data and other resources [1].

GRID Computing is primarily a user beneficial notion, some of the benefits being the following:

- Organizations, as well as end users, are enabled to aggregate resources with an entire IT infrastructure no matter where in the world they are located.
- Organizations can dramatically improve the quality and speed of the products they deliver, while reducing IT costs.
- Companies are enabled to access and share remote databases and data repositories. This is especially beneficial to the life sciences and engineering research communities.
- Widely dispersed organizations can easily collaborate on projects through their ability to share everything.
- A more robust and resilient IT infrastructure can be created. Such an infrastructure can respond better to minor or major disasters.
- Idle processing cycles in several desktop PCs distributed in various locations across multiple time zones can be harnessed.

Although, the establishment, management and exploitation of dynamic, cross-organizational GRID Systems require full interoperability and scalability, the security concern is also of great importance. The reason is that distributed applications are by definition more vulnerable than conventional ones since there are substantially more targets to attack in order to impact a single application [3].

Securing a Computational GRID that may be accessed by hundreds, or even, thousands of users, is critical. In this paper we present a review and an evaluation of the security architectures and mechanisms, which have been proposed for that purpose. In section 2 we emphasize on the security challenges as well as the security requirements in GRID Computing, in section 3 we present a review of existing security architectures and mechanisms and we evaluate them in terms of the above-mentioned requirements. Finally, in section 4 we conclude the paper.

2 Security Challenges and Requirements in GRID Computing

The overall motivation for GRID Computing is to enable access to, and sharing of, resources and services across wide area networks. This motivation incorporates known security challenges and requirements but also introduces new, thus necessitating the development of security architectures for the GRID.

2.1 Security Challenges

The security challenges in GRID environments can be categorized as follows [4]:

1. *Integration.* In order to build secure GRID Systems, the mechanisms being employed must be flexible and dynamic so as to facilitate the integration of security architectures and models implemented across platforms and hosting environments.
2. *Interoperability.* GRID services that traverse multiple domains and hosting environments need to be able to interact with each other, thus introducing the need for interoperability at protocol, policy and identity level.
3. *Trust relationships.* In order to solve the trust relationship problem in a GRID environment, it is necessary to support mechanisms for defining, managing and enforcing trust policies among the participants in a GRID System.

2.2 Security Requirements

The security challenges presented in the previous subsection lead to specific security requirements. These requirements may differ amongst GRID Systems, depending on the defined security policies and the type of applications and services used. The most important security requirements are [2], [4]:

- *Confidentiality.* Ensure non-disclosure of messages traveling over the network, to unauthorized entities.
- *Integrity.* Ensure that recipient entities may detect unauthorized changes made to messages.
- *Privacy.* Allow both a service or resource requestor and provider to define and enforce privacy policies.
- *Identification.* Associate each entity with a unique identifier.
- *Authentication.* Verify the identity of a participant entity to an operation or request.
- *Single logon.* Relieve an entity that has successfully completed the authentication process once, from the need to participate in re-authentication upon subsequent accesses to other participant systems in the GRID.
- *Authorization.* Allow for controlling access to resources or services based on authorization policies attached to each entity (e.g. resource or service).
- *Delegation.* Allow transfer of privileges (e.g. access rights) between entities.
- *Assurance.* Provide means to qualify the security level that can be expected from a hosting environment.
- *Autonomy.* Allow entities to have full control over their local security policies without compromising the overall GRID System's security.
- *Policy exchange.* Allow entities to dynamically exchange security policy information (e.g. authentication requirements).
- *Firewall traversal.* Provide mechanisms for traversing firewalls between administrative boundaries.
- *Secure logging.* Provide all services, including security services themselves, with facilities for time stamping and secure logging.

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- *Manageability*. Provide the appropriate tools for managing security mechanisms and policies.

3 GRID Security Architectures

Security is critical for the widespread deployment and acceptance of Computational GRIDs. Although several security architectures for the GRID environment have been proposed, none of them fulfills in a satisfactory way the entire list of security requirements.

This section provides an overview of existing security architectures, evaluating each of them in terms of the security issues raised in section 2. More specifically, the security mechanisms that each architecture implements are associated with the security requirements that they fulfill, commenting on their effectiveness, maturity and trust.

3.1 The Security Architecture for Open GRID Services

3.1.1 The Open GRID Services Architecture (OGSA)

The Open GRID Services Architecture (OGSA) is the result of research work aiming to produce a GRID system architecture that integrates GRID and Web services, concepts and technologies. An initial set of technical specifications has been proposed by the Globus Project and IBM, and has been recently put forward at the Global GRID Forum for discussion and refinement. At the same time, a strategy for addressing security issues within the OGSA is being developed aiming to comprise the security architecture for OGSA.

3.1.2 Proposed Security Architecture

The efforts described above led to an important conclusion regarding the proposed security architecture for OGSA: Abstraction of security components in a single security model is the only way to give organizations the necessary breathing space so as to be able to utilize existing investments in security technologies while communicating with others in a GRID environment.

Therefore, the basic principles that should underlie the GRID security model are [4]:

- developing a security model to secure GRID services in general, and
- developing security specific services built to provide the necessary functionality.

To fulfil the above basic principles, the GRID security model should take into account several aspects of GRID services invocation. This is possible through the various components of the GRID Security Model (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Components of the GRID Security Model [4]

3.2 GRID Security Infrastructure (GSI)

3.2.1 The Globus Toolkit

The Globus Toolkit was developed under the Globus Project, a research effort that introduces fundamental technologies required for building GRIDs. This toolkit comprises a set of components that implement basic services for security, resource allocation, resource management etc. GRID Security Infrastructure or GSI is the name given to Globus security services.

3.2.2 Proposed Security Architecture

I. Foster et al. proposed in 1998 a security architecture for Computational GRIDs [5]. This work constitutes the base of many GRID security architectures that were proposed later on, one of them being the GSI. Next we present the basic features of the GSI [8] [9].

Certificates constitute a central concept in GSI authentication as every entity on the GRID (e.g. user, process, resource) is identified by an X.509 certificate. Each certificate includes a key pair and must be signed by a Certification Authority (CA) in order to verify and validate the binding between the entity and the key pair.

GSI uses the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol for mutual authentication, although the use of Secure Socket Layer (SSL) is also possible. In both cases GSI must convert the global identity of involved parties in order to be recognizable to each local naming structure that a remote site may use, like login name or Kerberos. By default GSI does not establish encrypted communication, although the provision of that feature is very simple if confidentiality is required.

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An entity may delegate a subset of its rights to another entity by creating a temporary identity called a proxy. The proxy holds a temporary certificate signed by the user or a previous proxy in order to achieve authentication to remote sites. This situation creates a chain of signatures terminating with the CA, which issued the initial certificate. The duration of the proxy's life is limited in order to control the use of resources.

GSI architecture enables the "single sign-on" procedure for each user on the GRID and allows entities to access remote resources on behalf of the user. Additionally, this architecture does not require changing the local security infrastructure and policy in each site that the GRID spans.

3.3 The Legion Security Architecture

3.3.1 The Legion System

The Legion project, developed at the University of Virginia, is an attempt to provide GRID services that create the illusion of a virtual machine. This virtual machine addresses key GRID issues such as scalability, programming ease, fault tolerance, security and site autonomy. The realization of the virtual machine illusion is achieved through the implementation of a middleware level right above the current local operating system. Legion is an object-oriented meta-system and, thus, is based on the principles of the object-oriented paradigm like inheritance, encapsulation and polymorphism. [2] [6]

3.3.2 Proposed Security Architecture

The basic unit in a Legion system is the object. Each entity in the system, for example processes, users, resources etc. is represented by an object. In order to provide security in such a system one has, primarily, to protect these objects as well as the communication among them.

The Legion Security Architecture is based on the following principles [6, 7]:

- The installation of Legion at a site should not compromise that site's security policies and goals.
- Legion must be configurable to the security needs of different organizations.
- Objects must have flexible access control mechanisms for authorizing and denying method calls.
- Legion should protect identities, as well as, minimize the dispersion of authority that delegation causes.
- The protection of integrity and privacy of underlying communications between objects must be guaranteed.

In general, the primary goal for the Legion security architecture is to enable participants in a GRID system to expose their resources in a manner compliant with their local policies. Next, we present the basic security mechanisms and policies that are used by the Legion Security Architecture towards this goal [7].

3.3.2.1 Identity

Identity is important to higher-level security services, such as access control, and is based on a unique, location-independent, Legion Object Identifier (LOID). By default the Legion Security Architecture stores an RSA key pair in one of the LOID's fields. This pair protects confidentiality and integrity of object communications through encryption and digital signatures respectively. In fact, a LOID includes an empty, unsigned X.509 certificate, which contains the key pair mentioned above. The X.509 certificate structure is used for two reasons: firstly, to enable the encoding of the key pair in a standard way and, secondly, to provide the infrastructure for the incorporation of Certification Authorities on demand of the local system. By integrating keys into LOIDs, Certification Authorities are rendered unnecessary although such an authority is still useful for establishing user identities, as well as, eliminating some kinds of public keys tampering.

3.3.2.2 Credentials

In a distributed object system the user may access resources indirectly thus requiring corresponding objects to be able to perform actions on his behalf. Though intermediate objects could, in principle, be given the user's private key, the risk involved is high. In order to eliminate that risk, Legion provides issuing of credentials to objects. A credential is a list of rights granted by the user to a specific object for a specific period of time. The latest poses a major concern as it actually defines the period during which a credential is vulnerable to theft or abuse. The shorter the period the less ease of use but the more secure way and vice versa.

3.3.2.3 Authentication

Authentication in the Legion system is realized through the use of credentials. When a requestor object wants to communicate with a target object then it casts an authentication credential, which is nothing more than the LOID of the target object signed by the requestor object.

3.3.2.4 Access Control

In a Legion system, access is the ability to call a method on an object. Access control is decentralized and each object is responsible for enforcing its own access control policy. In general all method calls to an object must first pass through the access control procedure (called "the MayI layer") before the target method (member function) is invoked. Only if the caller has the appropriate rights for the target method will the access control allow the method invocation to proceed.

3.3.2.5 Communications

A method call from one object to another can consist of multiple messages. These messages use one of a number of underlying transport layers (UDP/IP, TCP/IP) or platform-specific message passing services and must be transmitted without their unauthorized disclosure or modification occurring. A message may be sent three ways: in the *clear mode*, in *protected mode* or in *private mode*. In clear mode no encryption or other security mechanism is applied to the message. In protected mode

a message digest is generated in order to protect its integrity. Finally, in private mode the message is encrypted.

3.3.2.6 Object Management

As stated in section 3.3.1 the Legion system is implemented as a middleware over existing operating systems that have their own security mechanisms and policies. Therefore, it is crucial for the Legion system to be implemented in such a way that ensures its security policies and the OS's security policies do not compromise each other.

3.4 The Globe security architecture

3.4.1 Globe

Globe stands for *Global Object Based Environment*. As its name reveals it is a wide-area distributed system, which was developed in order to constitute a middleware level between the operating system and the application level, exactly as Legion does. The main characteristics of the Globe system are [10]:

- It is a uniform model for the support of distributed systems.
- It supports a flexible implementation framework.
- It is highly scalable.

Globe is based on Distributed Shared Objects (DSOs). A DSO is formed by the replication of a local object, which resides in a single address space to other address spaces, and is identified by a unique Object ID (OID). Each local object consists of five sub-objects: Semantics, Control, Replication, Communication and Security sub-object. Each copy of the local object stores all or part of the DSO's state (in the Semantics sub-object) and is called a *replica object*. Sometimes a replica object does not store the DSO's state at all but simply forwards the user requests to replicas that can execute them in which case it is called a *user proxy*.

Each user or programmer in a local system interacts with the DSO in the same way as if the original local object was stored in the local system. Separate sub objects of local objects control replication of local objects and communication between them, while the semantics sub object implements the main functionality of the local objects. The DSO notion is important as it gives the Globe objects the ability to be shared amongst different systems that form a wide area network in excess of their normal ability to be shared amongst the users of the same system [10].

3.4.2 Proposed security architecture

During the initial development phase of the Globe Security Architecture, security issues concerning wide-area distributed systems were categorized in three major groups [11]:

- *Secure binding*. Verification of the local and replica objects being part of a certain DSO and association of the DSO to real world entities.
- *Platform security*. Protection of hosts from malicious mobile code and protection of mobile code from malicious hosts.
- *Secure method invocation*. User authentication and access control, communications protection and reverse access control (verification of replica objects trustworthiness).

The Globe Security Architecture is based on public key cryptography and digital certificates in order to address the above issues. In detail, DSOs, replicas and users are assigned public/private key pairs in order to be identified and are granted permissions through the use of the above-mentioned certificates. Next, we present the means through which Globe security architecture addresses the above mentioned issues [11].

3.4.2.1 *Secure binding*

As mentioned above, secure binding is concerned with securely associating a DSO to its public key, a replica to corresponding DSO and a DSO to corresponding real world entity. Secure association of a DSO to its public key is achieved through public key integration with the OID. The second issue is addressed by looking at the OID, at the replica certificate and its administrative certificate chain. Finally, the individual clients are responsible to establish a secure name binding for the DSOs they are using although external trust authorities could mediate this.

3.4.2.2 *Platform security*

Platform security is concerned with the protection of hosts from malicious mobile code and the protection of mobile code from malicious hosts. The former issue is addressed with the use of the java “sand boxing” technique in combination with code signing while the later is addressed with the use of the reverse access control mechanism or state signing.

3.4.2.3 *Secure method invocation*

Firstly, let’s clarify the concept of secure method invocation. A method invocation M issued by a user U and to be executed on a replica object R is said to be secure if the following conditions are met [11]:

- U is allowed to invoke M under the DSO’s security policy,
- R is allowed to execute M under the DSO’s security policy, and
- all the network communication between U and R takes place through a channel that preserves data integrity origin and destination authenticity and, possibly, also confidentiality.

Users can invoke methods on a DSO by simply calling those methods on their corresponding proxies. Then the replication, communication and security sub objects of their proxies work together to transform the users’ requests into remote method invocations, send them to appropriate replicas allowed to handle them, wait for the returned values and present these values to the users.

3.5 CRISIS

CRISIS is the security component for WebOS, a system that extends OS services such as security, remote process execution, resource management, and named persistent storage to support wide area distributed application.

3.5.1 Web OS

WebOS is a system developed at the University of Berkeley in order to extend conventional OS functionality in such a way as to simplify the use of geographically dispersed resources. The main features of WebOS are [12]:

- *Resource discovery.* Includes mapping a service name to multiple servers, balancing load among available servers, and maintaining enough state to perform fail over if a server becomes unavailable.
- *Wide area file system.* Extension of existing distributed file systems to wide area applications running in a secure HTTP name space.
- *Security and authentication.* Define a trust model providing both security guarantees and an interface for authenticating the identity of principals.
- *Process control.* Authenticate the identity of the requester and determine if the proper access rights are held while, at the same time, ensure that the process does not violate local system integrity and it does not consume more resources than the local system administrator permits.

3.5.2 Proposed security architecture

CRISIS assumes the presence of three basic entities, namely, *principals*, sources for requests such as machines or users, *objects*, representing global resources, and *reference monitors*, processes that determine whether or not to grant a given request. [13]

All statements in CRISIS, including statements of identity, statements of privilege, and transfer of privilege are encoded in X.509 certificates. These certificates are signed by the principal making the statement and then counter-signed by a principal of the signer's choosing. CRISIS employs two basic types of certificates: *identity certificates* (authentication and authorization) and *transfer certificates* (delegation).

CRISIS consists of a series of remote nodes (local systems). A *security manager* and *resource providers* run in each node. There are three kinds of resource providers each with its own set of reference monitors: *process managers*, that are responsible for executing jobs on requested nodes, *WebFS Servers*, that implement a cache coherent global file system, and *certification authorities*, that take requests for creating identity certificates.

In CRISIS all programs execute in the context of a *security domain*. A security domain is formed by the association of a login shell in a remote node with a set of certificates transmitted by the principal's home node/domain. Security managers are responsible for mediating access to all local resources and for mapping the above-mentioned credentials to security domains. In addition each principal in CRISIS can create roles that are principals granted a subset of his privileges (delegation).

3.6 GRID Security Architectures’ Evaluation

In the current subsection we present a comparative evaluation of the Security Architectures presented above, in terms of addressing the security requirements posed in section 2 (Table 1). It should be noted that the aforementioned evaluation is of an empirical nature and does not involve certain metrics.

Table 1. GRID Security Architectures’ Evaluation.

<i>Security Requirement</i>	<i>GSI</i>	<i>Legion Security Architecture</i>	<i>Globe Security Architecture</i>	<i>CRISIS</i>
Confidentiality	High	High	Medium	High
Integrity	High	High	Medium	High
Privacy	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Identification	High	High	High	High
Authentication	High	High	High	High
Single logon	High	Low	Low	Low
Authorization	Medium	High	High	High
Delegation	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Assurance	Low	Low	High	Medium
Autonomy	High	High	High	Medium
Policy exchange	Low	Low	Low	Low
Firewall traversal	Low	Low	Low	Low
Secure logging	Low	Low	Low	Low
Manageability	Low	Low	Medium	Medium

One would note that only four of the five Security Architectures described are evaluated in the above Table. This is due to the fact that Open GRID Services Architecture and, thus, the corresponding Security Architecture, are currently in the phase of specifications. For this reason, an evaluation effort would be unwise. Such an evaluation will be possible only for specific implementations of the OGSA.

4 Conclusions

During the last decade the notion of GRID Computing has emerged from that of Distributed Computing. GRID architectures form the next logical step in computing infrastructure following a path from standalone systems to tightly linked clusters, enterprise-wide clusters and geographically dispersed computing environments. Although such architectures can be characterized as state-of-the-art technology, they are, at the same time, a major contributor to some of the problems associated with the design and implementation of a secure environment, especially when combined with the continuously increasing user mobility. By allowing users to access services from virtually anywhere, the universe of ineligible people who may attempt to harm the system is dramatically expanded.

Several security architectures have been described in the literature, some of them being evaluated in section 3 of this paper. The aim was to investigate to what extent the GRID security requirements (presented in section 2) were fulfilled by these architectures. The evaluation results were presented in *Table 1*.

It has been revealed that none of the proposed security architectures fulfill, in an acceptable way, the entire list of GRID security requirements. However, this is not unexpected since the area of 'GRID Security' is still in very early stages. Nevertheless, several security requirements are fulfilled through various security mechanisms. For instance, strong encryption mechanisms have been employed for ensuring the confidentiality, integrity and availability of information (GSI), intelligent techniques have been developed for identifying and authorizing entities (e.g. Legion, Globe), while some of the proposed architectures deal more successfully with elaborate security issues such as firewall traversal (e.g. OGSA security architecture).

References

1. Foster, I., Kesselman, C., Tuecke, S.: The Anatomy of the GRID. Enabling Scalable Virtual Organizations, *International J. Supercomputer Applications*, 15(3), 2001.
2. Foster, I., Kesselman, C.: *The GRID: Blueprint for a Future Computing Infrastructure*. Morgan Kaufman, 1999.
3. Johnston, W.E., Jackson, K.R., Talwar S.: Overview of security considerations for computational and data GRIDs. In: *Proceedings of the 10th IEEE International Symposium on High Performance Distributed Computing*, 2001.
4. Nagaratnam, N., Janson P., Dayka, J., Nadalin, A., Siebenlist, F., Welch, V., Foster, I., Tuecke, S.: *The Security Architecture for Open GRID Services*. Technical Paper, Open GRID Service Architecture Security Working Group (OGSA-SEC-WG), July 2002.
5. Foster, I., Kesselman, C., Tsudik, G., Tuecke, S.: A Security Architecture for Computational GRID. In the *Proceedings of the 5th ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security Conference*, pp. 83-92, 1998.
6. Chapin, S., Wang, C., Wulf, W., Knabe, F., Grimshaw, A.: A New Model of Security for Metasystems. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, Vol.15 (5-6), pp.713-722, 1999.
7. Ferrari, A., Knabe, F., Humphrey, M., Chapin, S., Grimshaw, A.: A Flexible Security System for Metacomputing Environments. Technical Report CS-98-36, Department of Computer Science, University of Virginia, December 1998.
8. Butler, R., Engert, D., Foster, I., Kesselman, C., Tuecke, S., Volmer, J., Welch, V.: A National-Scale Authentication Infrastructure, *IEEE Computer*, 33(12):60-66, 2000.
9. Tuecke, S.: *GRID Security Infrastructure Roadmap*. Internet Draft, February 2001.
10. van Steen, M., Homburg, P., Tanenbaum, A.S.: Globe: A Wide-Area Distributed System, *IEEE Concurrency*, January-March, 1999, pp. 70-78.
11. Popescu, B.C., van Steen, M., Tanenbaum, A.S.: A Security Architecture for Object-Based Distributed Systems. In the *Proceedings of the 18th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*, Las Vegas, NV, December 2002.
12. Vahdat, A., Anderson, T., Dahlin, M., Culler, D., Belani, E., Eastham, P., Yoshikawa, C.: WebOS: Operating System Services For Wide Area Applications. In the *Seventh IEEE Symposium on High Performance Distributed Computing*, July 1998.
13. Belani, E., Vahdat, A., Anderson, T., Dahlin, M.: The CRISIS Wide Area Security Architecture. In the *Proceedings of the 1998 USENIX Security Symposium*, January 1998.